

LANGUAGE ANXIETY IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AMONG TEENAGERS. DEVELOPMENT OF ACTIVE LEARNING BY POSITIVE ASPECTS OF ANXIETY IN SPEAKING TASKS AMONG ADOLESCENTS

Mirzayeva Mamura

Teacher, Almalyk branch of Tashkent state technical University named
after Islam Karimov

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Annotation: This study investigates positive aspects of anxiety in second language acquisition among Uzbek adolescents who are studying at 11 th grade in Tashkent region, Almalyk city. This case study has piloted aim to determine development of active learning via positive aspects of anxiety while doing classroom tasks. Data was collected during the academic year 2019-2020 from school learners by two self-report surveys. Participants of the study were all 15 learners in “Specialized” group and totaled 6 boys and 9 girls. The results showed that anxiety works not only for positive effect but also active learning development of school pupils.

Key words: SLA, FLL, crucial role, development of language, data, profile, learners, adolescent, positive aspect, self-study

The second language acquisition (SLA) requests from learners various factors which can be language environment, active input process and first language (L1) transformation etc. However human beings differ from each other according to their individual differences which contain: age, sex, aptitude, language learning strategies, language learning styles and personality which may effect second language acquisition positively or negatively. The differences are closely connected with each other and plays crucial role in SLA and foreign language learning (FLL) as well.

Personality is connected with human psychology and determines individual features of learner characteristics. Personality factors are the means of distinguishing one person from another and language teachers put personality factors into consideration while teaching second language because if relationship between personality factors and language learning is neglectful, negative influence will be brought for teaching and learning processes. Anxiety is a factor of personality that interferes with the learning procedure and closely connected with self-esteem, inhibition, risk taking. It is an emotion that shows effect on working and studying processes. As we are teaching English as a second language, learners experience anxiety when it comes to mostly speaking activities in front of group, doing tests or writing and reading tasks.

Instead of having great amount of research works carried out concerning the role of positive anxiety for the development of active learning in world level, there is lack of data has been collected about the same topic in Uzbekistan. For the purpose of the study I examined that to what extend anxiety affects students' nature or nurture ability and after implementing strategies for carrying out successful presentation, speaking skills I determined the role of facilitative anxiety for the development of active learning in speaking tasks.

Review of literature

1.1 Classification of anxiety

Inspite of becoming anxiety as a common sense there is no exact definition for it and the term comes with the feelings of worry, frustration, fear, uneasiness and nervousness. Anxiety is a subjective feeling which affects second language (L2) acquisition and performance (Brown, 2000, Dornyei, 2005, Horwitz, 2001). Shahila (2012) claims that there are two types of anxiety: "trait anxiety" and "state anxiety". But Gilbert (2011) presents three types with addition "situation-specific anxiety" that has been theorized to affect learners' learning.

- Trait anxiety is a stable part of individual personality and a permanent tendency for becoming anxious.
- "State anxiety". Second type of anxiety happens with the effect of some event or act which can be temporary or context-specific.
- The last one: "situation-specific anxiety" that learners feel because of some situation or event especially happens while taking tests or learning a new language.

Noles and Donovan (1997) suggested that learners who has no desire to speak will not progress as fast as learners who are more relaxed.

Recent researches proved that not all anxieties work for negative effect but they can give positive effect and facilitate learning. Two type of anxiety have been identified regarding its usefulness.

- Debilitative (harmful anxiety)
- Facilitative (helpful anxiety)

Positive factor of anxiety is considered facilitative anxiety which benefits in learning foreign languages while competing among learners, sometimes hinder their progress but other times motivates to study harder (Bailey, 1983). A recent study has been done by Jean-Mark Dewaele and Peter MacIntyre (2014) that found that lack of anxiety does not necessarily imply high level of enjoyment of language learning. Especially anxious learners try to achieve higher results rather than non-anxious peers this is why teachers should generate some anxiety in their learners to elicit better performance

1.2. Language anxiety in speaking.

A situation-specific anxiety as a foreign language anxiety stemming from the inherent linguistic deficit of L2 learners (Horwitz, 1986). MacIntyre (1999) defined the construct as the worry and negative emotional reaction which comes out while learning or using a second language. Studies claimed that anxiety may affect all stages: input level for concentrating and encoding information, processing stage contains resulting poor organization, storage and assimilation of information. This is why there is relationship between language anxiety and students' measure of achievement.

According to students' engagement in speaking activities, anxiety does not only affect low-level language learners, but it is a fact that it affects advanced speakers as well (Baker & MacIntyre 2000). Speaking in the target language seems the most threatening aspect of foreign language learning and that the lack of oral skills brings serious problems to language learners Ely (1986), MacIntyre & Gardner, (1989), Campbell (1991), Price (1991), Aida (1994). Although students have most interest in learning to communicate orally in the foreign language (Phillips, 1991), their anxieties may play minus roles. Labov (1969 in Tsui, 1996: 156) affirms that speaking in class is experienced by students as "high-risk" and "low-gain". As a matter of fact, one of the main problems of speaking anxiety is the negative influence which it has on the L2 performances and on the attitude toward the foreign language tasks. Avoidance behaviors may put the student in the condition of excluding himself from conversations and interactions with people of different cultures and languages, because they do not share a common lingua franca.

1.2 Strategies to reduce anxiety in classrooms

Dealing with state anxiety, which might occur, for example, when performing a speaking task in class or in real-life situations. This kind of anxiety might prevent students from enjoying practicing with peers, doing oral reports in class, or engaging in conversations with other English speakers (Woodrow, 2006).

Teachers play essential role for reducing learners' anxiety level rather than elevate them because anxiety is not just private phenomenon which is produced by individuals alone but it can be affected by external factors (Noormohammadi, 2009). Horwitz (2008) claims that so as to reduce students' anxious feelings, individual language learning sources should be identified which contain parental influence, comparison with peers, class arrangements. Cheng, Horwitz and Schallet (1999) suggest providing sufficient non-threatening and supportive instructional environment where high level of self-confidence occurs. Casado and Dereshivskiy (2001) noted about effective techniques:

- Making learners aware that being fluent and getting a good accent in target language tasks
- Providing positive reinforcement and creating relaxed classroom environment
- Helping more low-level language learners
- Using smaller classes to give help instructors identify students experiencing anxiety and giving enough support etc.

However as Horwitz and Young (1991) informed that activities cannot solve the anxiety problems deeply but reduce usual sort of overanxious problems this is why teachers should try to create learning conditions which will help to keep anxiety levels low.

Teachers should build opportunities for learners to work individually, in pairs, and in small groups before proceeding with speaking in a whole class, so that learners can modify what they want to express. They should think positively and remind your students that no one wants to spend time listening to a talk which is nonsense or engaging in a bad conversation. Encourage learners to see themselves as fluent and confident speakers and to remember that listeners want them to succeed. Experience builds confidence. Create opportunities for your students to build successes. At the same time, encourage your students to gain experience and to practice wherever and whenever they can by trying to respond to what their interlocutors say to them.

It's important to remind your students to never expect any strategy to work in a best level the first time they try it. Suggest that they apply and experiment with different strategies a few times to find the routine that that best minimizes their anxiety associated with speaking. Finally, help your students recognize that a "facilitative" anxiety can help them convey their message or ideas with energy and enthusiasm. That's important, because, if one is not enthusiastic about what he or she has to share, others also could not do. So encourage students to make the butterflies work for them (Huang, 2011).

Learners' profile

The participants of this study were all from specialized group and studying at 11th form. They were totaled 15 pupils and from this: girls' number contains 9 participants and boys' number showed 6 members. After asking about their motivational factors of second language learning, language practice period, the below given data was collected. All of them are non-native speakers and learning English for studying abroad, achieving educated person level, future career and living in foreign countries. Almost most of them know two languages and four of them have practice to speak more than two languages. Learners have been

learning English from 1st class and it was two years 11 members have been participating tutors to consolidate knowledge and achieve best results. Students' previous aim to enter university than living in foreign country, make friends etc. They have great interest to learn English via technologies, digital games, songs, movies, videos, collaborative tasks, presentations and interviews.

Design of study

In this section the design of the study includes two types of self-report surveys which were utilized from the design of Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety (Horwitz and Cope, 1986) with more exceptions. As a researcher I used the survey for pre-self-report survey (see Appendix A) and post self-report survey (see Appendix B) by adding goal related questions and by skipping not related questions as a frame for my surveys. First pre-self-report questions directed researcher to clarify participants' language anxiety level and reasons of debilitating anxiety and second one aimed at finding out the facilitative anxiety's role for development of active learning.

The study designs focuses on participants' beliefs, experiences and feelings in order to take reliable data for the phenomenon of anxiety associated with second language learning and after implementing anxiety reduce speaking strategies for manifesting debilitating anxiety to facilitative anxiety while teaching, helped to take enough data to prove research question.

Data collection

The case study was carried out during normal school days with assistance of other English language teachers. We know that students in specialized groups study English lesson four or five even more hours in a day this is why I had no difficulty for time to carry out my research work. In addition I work at the school and my colleagues helped me a lot in all conditions.

The data collection started from informing learners about pre-self-report survey which is considered as the first part of the research and gathering learners' answers. This questions for finding out students anxiety level and harmful anxiety reasons showed that most learners are adolescents who are between childhood and adulthood and changing minds and characteristics have high level of fear, losing ideas while speaking, shyness mostly among girls, afraid of doing mistakes and others' laughing at them and taking bad marks as well. From 15 learners have strong self-confidence since they have IELTS results. Next step was aimed at implementing anxiety reduce strategies and informing and directing learners about facilitative anxiety by telling to be competitive to do speaking tasks in order to take high results and working hard in so as not to show anxiety level after creating friendly atmosphere by teacher.

The last stage was spent to gather participants' opinions about facilitative anxiety's role for development of active learning by doing second self-report survey. The results showed that 11 students out of 15 had a friendly manner, motivation for speaking tasks by facilitative anxiety and manifested anxiety. Both survey results are counted according to chosen answers by learners and if most learners choose the same answer it means that the answer will show its significance character regarding aims of survey.

Conclusion

Research has shown that effects of anxiety can adversely affect person's aptitude to acquire second language process especially oral communication for students' speaking English. Anxiety mostly directs deficits not only in learning but also in performance. This is because teachers should be aware of potential effects of anxiety on learners' abilities to learn any second language and should create friendly, comfortable atmosphere for self-confident and manifesting debilitating type to facilitative anxiety. The findings proved that the anxiety could work for learners' active learning and overcoming speaking skill difficulties. Of course it happened after my beneficial strategies, attempts then showed sufficient results.

Applying the strategies into teaching worked efficiently

because students understood the crucial aim. They tried to become active not only in order to take high results in second language acquisition but also to gain experience, knowledge because they are coming across puberty period which affects their feelings of entering universities which is considered prestige for them. Personally I believe that every single teacher who loves, appreciates teaching can find ways to solve any kind of problems and can help anxiety to work in positive aspects for learners.

For future research of the same topic I can propose that reading, listening and writing skills are also crucial field for proving positive aspects of anxiety, furthermore it will be better if attention will be paid to teaching methodology and other factors which effect on anxiety like risk-taking, inhibition self-esteem and extroversion and introversion in Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Dornyei, Z & Ryan, S. (2005). The psychology of the language learner revisited. *Anxiety. Language anxiety*, 175, 176, 177.
2. Gilbert, W. (2011). How anxiety effects second language acquisition of high school students. *Factors that affect second language acquisition. How anxiety results to student's classroom experience. Effects of anxiety on second*

- language learning. Strategies to reduce anxiety in classrooms, 8, 12, 13, 16.
3. Horwitz, E & Young, D (1991). Foreign language classroom anxiety: from theory and research to classroom implications, 27-39.
 4. Hossein, N. (2005). The effect of power point presentations on student learning and attitudes. Power point presentations and student attitude. Effect of power point presentations on student learning, 55, 58.
 5. Huang, L. (2011). Seven tips for helping learners minimize anxiety in speaking, 4.
 6. MacIntyre, P & Gardner, R. (1989). The subtle effects of language anxiety on cognitive processing in the second language. Language learning, 283, 284.
 7. MacIntyre, P, Clement, R and Kimberly, A, Noles (1989). Affective variables, attitude and personality in context. Self-confidence and anxiety, 277.
 8. Pam, M. (2013). Facilitative anxiety. Signs of anxiety, 8.
 9. Sladana, Z. (2014). The importance of oral presentations for university students. Supporting students to develop better communication and presentation skills, 469-470.
 10. Zafar, Sh. (2012). Individual learner differences and second language acquisition: a review. Personality. Anxiety, 643, 644.